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Original article

Difficulties Encountered With Fungal Keratitis

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Abstract

Purpose: The object of this work is to study the difficulties encountered with patients with fungal keratitis.

Subjects and Methods: All cases with keratitis attending the Outpatient Clinic of Ophthalmology Department of Tanta University during the summer months from the first of May to the end of August of the year 2000 were selected and carefully examined and cases with mycotic keratitis were further examined and investigated.

Results: Out of a total 8030 attendants during this period with different complaints, there were 50 cases (0.62 %) with mycotic keratitis and 75 cases (0.93 %) of non-mycotic origin that is the control group. Results revealed that mycotic keratitis is common in age group between 40 – 60 years. Laboratory findings were positive in 80 % for fungal growth and negative in 20 % of cases in spite of their typical clinical findings for diagnosis and their improvement with antifungal therapy.

Conclusion: Mycotic keratitis is most frequent in farmers, patients proceeded with organic trauma. Not all laboratory findings were positive, not all the cases have the typical findings for clinical diagnosis and not all the cases improved with anti fungal therapy even after culture and sensitivity tests.

Key Words: fungal keratitis

Introduction:

Mycotic keratitis is a severe problem in most of the developing countries; where as specific antifungal agents are expensive and commercially unavailable as ready compounds for topical ocular use. Other problems included difficulties in its clinical diagnosis, laboratory results and treatment ⁽¹⁾.

According to predisposing factors, clinical features and response to treatment, fungal corneal pathogens were divided into filamentous fungi, yeast, yeast like and dimorphic fungi ⁽²⁾. The most common filamentous fungi causing keratomycosis are *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, *Curvularia*, *Alternaria*

and *Cladosporium*, while *Candida albicans* is the commonest form of yeast ⁽³⁾.

Identification of pathogenic corneal fungi is performed either by microscopic stained corneal scraps or by their cultural features ⁽⁴⁾.

Aim Of The Work:

The aim of this work is to evaluate the difficulties encountered with mycotic keratitis either in clinical diagnosis, laboratory findings or treatment.

Patients & Methods:

Fifty cases with resistant corneal ulcers were selected from the outpatient clinic of Tanta University Ophthalmology Hospital suspected and

diagnosed clinically to be of fungal origin depending on some clinical criteria ^(5,6) including:

- * Thick area of keratitis.
- * Thick hypopyon "coagulum", with or without level.
- * Immune rings.
- * Satellite lesions.
- * Stromal infiltrate with feathery edge.
- * Healing usually with dense leucoma with large solitary BV.
- * Area of epithelial defect is usually smaller than stromal infiltration. These cases were submitted to a complete ophthalmological examination, including pen light examination, slit lamp examination using direct oblique, scleral scatter, and retroillumination techniques. Corneal staining with fluorescein and rose Bengal was done.
- * History taking for some risk factors such as recent drug intake (prolonged antibiotics and local or systemic corticosteroids); corneal Trauma whether organic or non organic; systemic diseases (diabetes, tuberculosis, cancer,); ocular surgery; local eye diseases such as glaucoma and the time of onset of complaints till examination.
- * Laboratory investigations: -all cases diagnosed clinically as fungal keratitis were submitted to:
- * *Sampling:* Under surface anaesthesia, the active edge and the bed of ulcer were scraped using platinum spatula or sterile surgical blade (No.15) with the aid of slit lamp biomicroscopy or surgical microscope to ensure that adequate corneal material was obtained and to avoid corneal perforation. Some ulcers were very soft, sticky and mucoid in consistency, so disposable calcium alginate cotton tipped sterile applicators were used for those cases.
- * *Isolation media:* Sabouraud's glucose agar was prepared with 0.05 %

chloramphenicol, autoclaved, spread on sterile Petri plates. Plates were incubated at room temperature, fungal growth was identified then sensitivity tests were carried out in vitro by using these available antifungal agents shown in table (1).

Table (1) Antifungal agents used in sensitivity tests:

Trade name	Scientific name	Concentration
Diflucan(Pfizer comp.)	Fluconazole	2mg/ml
Fungizone (Squibb comp.)	Amphotericin B	2.5 mg/ml
Sporonox (Janssen-Cilag)	Itraconazole	10 mg/ml

* Some examples for patients with mycotic keratitis and plates of isolated fungi are shown in figures (1),(2).

• According to the results of sensitivity tests, the appropriate antifungal agent shown in table 1 prepared for topical use were started as one drop hourly during the waking hours up to 5 days. Once healing was observed (a decrease in ulcer size or reepithelization and improvement of patient's complaints), the dose was reduced to 3 times daily for 2 weeks.

The treatment regimen used for all cases was:

- Fluconazole (2mg/ml). Topically till the results of culture appear.
- Continue the specific treatment according to culture's results.

* Adjunctive therapy:

- Cyclopentolate (Thilo) eye drops, 3 times/day.
- Isoptofenicol (Alcon) eye drops, 5 times /day.
- Thilotears gel (Thilo) , twice daily.
- Corticosteroid drops (FML from Allergen) twice daily were added if there is immune ring or associated uveitis in addition to topical and

systemic non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.

•For cases not responding to treatment within the first week; a debridement of superficial corneal layers was done to enhance good penetration of antifungal therapy.

Results:

Age & Sex:

The mean age for cases of mycotic keratitis was 49.18 ± 2.28 years; as regards the sex, males represented 66%(33 cases) while females were 34%(17 cases) of total 50 cases.

Laboratory results: Table (2) revealed that *Aspergillus* species constituted the majority of cases with positive cultures. *Aspergillus flavus* in 28% (14 cases) and *Aspergillus niger* in 16 % (8 cases) and the least frequent species was *Candida albicans* 2 % (only 1 case) of total 50 cases . Negative cultures occurred in 20 % of cases inspite of their improvement with antifungal therapy and their typical clinical findings for diagnosis.

Risk factors:

Table (3) showed that Trauma whether organic or non-organic was the most frequent risk factor for both of mycotic (52%) and non-mycotic (72%) groups. Organic ocular trauma was the most frequent risk factor in mycotic keratitis (in 32% of cases) while non-organic trauma was the most risky for the control group (44%). Other risk factors included ocular surgery, which represented 30% of mycotic cases compared to 0 % among non-mycotic group. Prolonged local antibiotics uptake was risky for 6% of mycotic keratitis compared to no one among non mycotic group. Systemic diseases represented the least frequent risk for mycotic keratitis (2% of the cases) while it was 8% in 3. *Candida albicans*.

non-mycotic keratitis. All cases of mycotic keratitis that had a history of ocular surgery had a mild course of corticosteroid therapy except in 8 cases that had a prolonged heavy course.

Table (2) Types of fungal infections among the cases

Typo of Fungus	No	%
<i>Asporgillus flavus</i>	14	28
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	8	16
<i>Mucor racemsus</i>	7	14
<i>Cladosporium Spherospermtim</i>	6	12
<i>Penicillium lanosurn</i>	4	8
<i>Candida albicans</i>	1	2
Negative culture	10	20
Total	50	100

Table (3) Risk factors

Risk Factors	Mycotic Keratitis		Non Mycotic	
	No	%	No	%
Systemic dis.	1	2	6	8
Ocular Surg.	15	30	0	0
OcularTrauma (organic)	10	32	21	28
Ocular rauma (no Organic)	10	20	33	44
Prolonged Local ntibiotic	3	6	0	0
More than one factor	3	4	0	12
No Obvious Causes	2	4	0	0
Total	44	102	60	92

Right eye of case: 1
Mycotic Keratitis (*Mucor Racemosus*) With Dermatocoele

Right eye of case : 2
Central mycotic keratitis (*Penicillium Lansosum*) with epithelial defect & Stromal Infiltration

Right eye of case : 3
Elevated area of mycotic krratitis (*Candida Albicans*)

Right eye of case : 4
Mycotic Keratitis (*Asprgillus Flavus*) with perforation

Right eye of case : 5
Mycotic Keratitis (*Aspergillus Flavus*) with hypopyon

Figure.2: Some examples for plates of isolated fungi.

Fate and complications:

•Eight patients (16%) showed complete healing, 9 patients (18%) showed healing with faint nebulae , 26 patients (52%) showed healing with dense vascularized leucoma , 3 patients with descematocele (6%) , 2 patients (4%) with perforation and 2 patients (4%) ended by endophthalmitis .

Discussion

Corneal infections including fungal types are responsible for about 50% of corneal scarring in the developing world which is a significant cause of blindness ⁽⁸⁾. Mycotic keratitis is a growing health problem in the developing countries representing from one third up to 56% of total ocular infection ⁽⁹⁾. World health organization reported that about 10 millions all over the world were blind due to corneal infections in its program for prevention of blindness (Global initiative vision by the year 2020) ⁽⁹⁾.

Age and Sex:

•In the present work about half the cases of mycotic keratitis were at the age group between 40 –60 years and males were about two times more affected than females. These findings were close to that of Chander J. and Sharma A. , 1994 ⁽⁵⁾ in their study in India where as they concluded that fungal keratitis affected males three times more than females and were more frequent in the age group from 50 to 60 years. Other studies ^(7 & 10) revealed that fungal keratitis affected males more than females and were more common in those aged >20 years up to 50 years. Males are more affected because of their more activity and movement in the surrounding environment which expose them to different risks such as corneal trauma. There were no significant statistical differences between cases of mycotic

keratitis and those of non-mycotic keratitis as regards the age groups and sex.

As regards laboratory findings for fungal growth It was found that 80% of patients were positive, while 20 % were negative inspite of their typical clinical findings and their improvement with antifungal therapy. These may explained by some fungi present in deep stroma couldn't be obtained if superficial scraping was done or if scraping was obtained only from one area. These findings were in consistence with Chander and Sharma, 1994 ⁽⁵⁾ who reported that 16.39 % of their patients showed negative fungal growth inspite of their typical clinical findings for fungal keratitis.

•**For the type of fungus isolated;** it was found that *Aspergillus* species were the most common (44%) either *A. flavus* (28%) or *A. niger* (16%); which was in agreement with Chander and Sharma ⁽⁵⁾ in India. They demonstrated that *Aspergillus species* constituted the majority (40.1%) of fungal growth in their study. Other study ⁽¹²⁾ in Saudia Arabia demonstrated that *Aspergillus species* occurred in 41%. These findings may be explained by the more spread of *Aaspergillus species* in the environment specially spores, which can survive hot and dry weather for long time. *Aspergillus species* existed in the soil and animal skin so, they were more frequent among the farmers in this study.

•Among *Aspergillus species* it was found that *Aspergillus flavus* constituted 28% and *Aspergillus Niger* 16%. This was consistent with the findings of other study ⁽¹³⁾ that demonstrated 17.1%*A. flavus* and 13.7%*A. niger* .

•*Candida albicans* were the least frequent type (only in 2%), that is in agreement with other study ⁽¹⁴⁾ which reported that *Candida* and *Fusarium species* were the least common in their study.

•This work reported that among cases of mycotic keratitis, organic trauma was the most prevalent risk factor (32%), followed by ocular surgery in 30% of cases then the non-organic trauma in 20% followed by the use of topical antibiotics in 6% and systemic disease (such as diabetes) was the least frequent in only 2%. Farmers were more exposed to organic trauma (with rice or corn stems or others) during farming so they were more exposed to mycotic keratitis. As regards the risk of ocular surgery among the cases, fungal contamination might occur preoperative in those cases with negative cultures or postoperative due to lowered body immunity (by the stressful surgery) and or the use of a course of local and systemic corticosteroids with the surgery. In consistence with our findings, ocular trauma was the most frequent risk either for mycotic or non mycotic keratitis in other studies ^(11, 13, 15, 16).

Recommendation:

•Restriction of the abuse of topical or systemic corticosteroids or antibiotics.

•Mycotic keratitis should be suspected in every patient with a corneal lesion, specially the

Resistant one and should be ruled out before commencing steroids and antibiotics.

•For a successful treatment , we need:

A- Proper early clinical diagnosis.

B- Proper laboratory tests that helped by deep scraping of the ulcer or even biopsy .

C- Initiating a broad spectrum antifungal drug till laboratory findings prove the Specific drug.

D-Proper frequency of antifungal drugs.

References

- 1- Martin MJ, Rahman MR, and Johnson GJ. Fungal keratitis. *Int Ophthalmol* 1995; 96 ; 19 (5) : 299-302.
- 2- Kwon-Chung KJ, Bennett JE: *Medical Mycology*. Lea & Febiger. Philadelphia, London.1992; 162-169.
- 3- Al-Hussaini, M.K : Studies on keratomycosis. MD Thesis, Ophthalmology 1990 Dep., Fac. Of Medicine. Assiut University. .
- 4- O'Day DM. Fungal keralitis" in : Prepose JS , Holland GN, wilhelmus KR,eds .*Ocular infection & immunity* . . Mosby, Philadelphia,1996;. P: 1048 – 1061.
- 5- Chander J. and Sharma A .Prevalence of fungal corneal ulcers in Northern India. *Infection*. 1994; 22(4) 207 – 209.
- 6- Thomas PA. Mycotic keralitis :an underestimated mycosis " . *J . Med. & vet . Mycolosy*,1994 32 (4) 235 –256 .
- 7- Moharram A.M, Abdel Kader M I , Al Hussaini AK. and Alghalibi S.M. Studies on Mycotic keratitis in Assiut Governorat . The second international conference on fungi " Hopes & challenges. Cairo .1999 29th Sept. – 1st Oct. Vol. (1) :P133 –146.
- 8- Prashant M., Gullapalli N. and Rao M . corneal ulcer : Diagnoses and Management " *Community eye Health*, 1999 Vol. 12 No. 30.
- 9- Gorden JJ. External eye infections. *Community eye Health*, 1999 Vol. 12, No.30.
- 10- Venugopal PL, Venugopal TI,et al. " Mycotic keratitis in Madras " *Indian J Pathol Microbiol*,1989 Jul; 32(3) :190-7.
- 11- Vajpayee RB , Ray M , Panda A, et al.Risk factors for presumed microbial keratitis: a case- control study ". *Cornea* ,1999 Sep; 18(5):565-9.
- 12- Khairallah SH, Byrenka E and Tabbara KF. Fungal keratitis in Saudia Arabia". 1992 *Doc Ophthalmol* ; 79 (3):269-76.
- 13- Wong TY, Fong KS, Tan DT (1996): A 5-year retrospective study on mycotic keratitis in Singapore national eye center.
- 14- Upadhyay MP Karmacharya PC ,et al. Epidemiologic characteristics , predisposing factors, and etiologic diagnosis of corneal ulceration in Nepal. *Am J Ophthalmol* 1991 Jan 15; 111 (1).
- 15- Rosa Rh , Miller D and Alfonso EC. The changing spectrum of fungal Keratitis in South Florida . *Ophthalmology* 1994 Jun; 101(6): 1005-13.
- 16- Rinivasan M, Gonzales CA, George C, et al. Epidemiology and etiological diagnosis of corneal ulceration in Madurai, South India". *Br J Ophthalmol* 1997;Nov; 81 (11): 965-71.

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